

1 **Wnt6, Bmp7, and Fgf19 define commitment to the TE in human pluripotent stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Wnt6,
9 Bmp7 and Fgf19 as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic
10 stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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